

Challenges ahead in the preparation of Bacterial Cellulose film from fruit juices

Focusing on the production of BC cellulose from apple juice (*Mauls Domestica*).

Dr Reza Rezaei Mokarram¹
Dr Mahmoud Soti Khiabani²
MSc Fatemeh Salek Mahdavi³
Jaber Safaei⁴

¹ Tabriz University

² Tabriz University

³ Tabriz University

⁴ Independent Researcher

ABSTRACT

Since the production of bacterial nanocellulose has a high cost, trying to find methods for its economic and mass production is one of the important challenges of the food and pharmaceutical industries. Also, the difference in the physical and chemical properties of nanocellulose obtained from different culture environments provides a wider variety of applications. The use of waste from food industries such as fruit juice concentrate factories can be a good option for mass and economic production of bacterial nanocellulose. Therefore, in this article, we have discussed how to produce cellulose film from fruit extracts and optimization and leading problems. And finally, we have analyzed the laboratory findings by comparing and reviewing other articles.

In this article, the steps and method of preparing cellulose film from fruit extracts are presented. Then the laboratory findings in the preparation of cellulose film from apple juice, watermelon juice and carrot juice, which included successful and unsuccessful repetitions, were reviewed and analyzed. This analysis is based on the test data and the review of related articles to find the cause and provide solutions to the problems. The results of the experiment showed that adjusting the pH of apple juice by sodium hydroxide prevents the growth of *Acetobacter xylinus*. Also, the presence of *Ursolic acid* in the apple skin has antibacterial properties and has a negative effect on the amount of cellulose film production. Also, the weight efficiency of the cellulose film produced in fruit juices is more than that of histrine culture medium.

Keywords: Bacterial Cellulose, nanocellulose, BC cellulose, Cellulose film, *Acetobacter xylinus*

INTRODUCTION

Cellulose is one of the most abundant biopolymers on the planet. This polymer forms the primary structure of the cell wall of lignocellulosic materials and from the structural point of view, it is a linear homopolysaccharide with high molecular weight. Cellulose is composed of linked D-glucopyranose units with 1-4 linkages. The long chain, glucose dimer (cellobiose) is the repeating unit of this polymer. Each unit has six hydroxyl groups and two glycosidic bonds, which are connected through intermolecular and intermolecular hydrogen bonds. Bacterial cellulose is the purest form of cellulose and does not contain lignin, hemicellulose, extractives and other cell wall compounds. Bacterial cellulose synthesis is performed by Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria such as *Acetobacter*, *Agrobacterium*, *Alkaligenes*, *Pseudomonas*, *Rhizobium*, *Aerobacter*, *Azotobacter* and *Salmonella* in aqueous environments containing sugar sources. Bacterial cellulose, cellulose with a high percentage of purity and crystallinity, has unique physical, chemical and mechanical properties such as high water holding capacity, high surface area, high elasticity, high mechanical resistance and wet strength, and high adaptability. Today, researchers are trying to produce bacterial nanocellulose from fruits and industrial food waste that contain various types of sugars. This effort is to increase the production and reduce the cost and finally to economize the production of bacterial

nanocellulose and on the other hand to obtain nanocellulose with different physical and chemical properties for different applications, the most important of which is the use in the food and pharmaceutical industry.

Table. 1. Adjusting the pH of culture media Trial 1

sample	Initial pH	Adjusted pH	pH adjustment additive
Apple juice	4.1	5.6	NaOH
Watermelon juice	5.7	5.7	None
Carrot juice	6.6	5.6	HCl

Cellulose film production procedure

- 1- Preparation of fruit juice and filtration (separation of pulp and suspended particles)
- 2- Measuring and adjusting the pH of fruit extract
- 3- Autoclave at a temperature of 121 degrees Celsius for 15 minutes at a pressure of 15 psi (Sterilization of culture medium)
- 4- Cooling to ambient temperature, then bacterial inoculation
- 5- Incubate at 28°C for 7 to 10 days
- 6- Removing the prepared cellulose film and washing with distilled water, then washing with 0.1 normal Sodium hydroxide solution for one hour.
- 7- Wet weight measurement of cellulose film
- 8- Drying in the oven Then measure the dry weight
- 9- Physicochemical tests of the final cellulose film and comparison with the cellulose produced in HS Culture medium

Trial 1:

According to the test procedure, a 300 ml sample was prepared from three extracts of watermelon, apple and carrot placed in an incubator.

Observations:

Watermelon and carrot samples were moldy and no cellulose film was formed on them for the apple juice sample no visible change was observed and no cellulose film was formed.

Analytical and probabilistic reasons

1- Weak sterilization of the replication medium and incubator has caused contamination of the samples or Contamination of the samples during the inoculation stage

2- The pH of carrot juice was adjusted by HCL 5 normal and its pH range was adjusted from 6.6 to 5.6. Watermelon juice was at pH 5.7, which we did not changed it, Apple juice was adjusted from pH 4.1 to 5.6 by sodium hydroxide shown in **Table.1**. The possible cause of the different behavior of apple juice can be the presence of sodium hydroxide, which prevents the proliferation and growth of bacteria and mold, and as a result, does not produce cellulose film.

Fig. 1. Cellulose films obtained from medium culture of HS and carrot juice and watermelon juice
Table. 2. Adjusting the pH of culture media Trial 2

sample	Initial pH	Adjusted pH	pH adjustment additive
Apple juice	4.05	5.6	NaOH
Watermelon juice	5.8	5.8	None
Carrot juice	6.7	5.6	HCl
HS	6.4	5.6	HCl

Trial 2:

In the second repetition, a 300 ml sample of each extract was prepared and 300 ml samples in HS culture medium (ingredients: peptone 0.5%, yeast extract 0.5%, citric acid 0.115%, Na₂HPO₄ 0.27% and 4 d-glucose 2% in 300 ml of distilled water) was also prepared as a base sample. The purpose of measuring the behavior of the samples compared to the base culture medium, in this repetition, more attention was paid to the sterilization of the medium, and bacteria were inoculated in the culture medium.

Observations:

Cellulose films weighing 17.5 and 19.5 grams were obtained in two culture mediums of watermelon and carrot .HS culture mediums obtained 11.3 grams of Cellulose film. No film was formed in the culture medium of apple juice and there is no visible corruption in it.

Analytical and probabilistic reasons

1- Apple juice has antibacterial properties. Ursolic acid (5-ring Three Terpenoid) found in apple skin has antimicrobial properties against many strains of bacteria, fungi and viruses.

2- Adjusting the pH by adding sodium hydroxide prevents the growth of bacteria. This reason was strengthened in the second iteration and the decision was made not to use sodium hydroxide in the next iteration for the apple juice sample.

Table. 3. Adjusting the pH of culture media Trial 3

sample	Initial pH	Adjusted pH	pH adjustment additive
Apple juice 1	4.2	5.7	NaOH
Apple juice 2	4.2	4.2	None
Watermelon juice	5.6	5.6	None
Carrot juice	6.5	5.7	HCl
HS	6.4	6.4	None

Trial 3:

Two 300 ml samples were prepared from each extract and two 300 ml samples were prepared from Schram's histrine culture medium.

In this repetition, the pH of apple juice after filtering was measured as 4.2

A sample without pH change was autoclaved and placed in an incubator.

And one sample was set to 5.6 by adjusting the pH with sodium hydroxide.

Watermelon juice and carrot juice culture medium samples were prepared according to the previous repetition procedure and placed in the incubator.

Observations

Apple extract with pH 4.2, cellulose film weighing 13.5 grams was obtained. Cellulose film was not formed in apple juice sample with pH 5.6. For the samples of carrot juice and watermelon, cellulose film similar to the previous iteration was obtained. 24 grams of carrot juice and 22 grams of watermelon and 16.8 grams of cellulose film were obtained for the HS culture medium.

Analytical and probabilistic reasons

The apple juice sample that was not pH adjusted had a lower contact surface with air than the other 3 samples, which had a negative effect on the amount of film produced.

Results and Discussion

1-It is possible to produce cellulose BC film in the culture medium of fruit extracts in the pH range of 4 to 6. This pH range includes many fruit extracts that can be used for the production of cellulose film.

2-Adjusting the pH of the culture medium with sodium hydroxide has a negative effect on the growth of bacteria and the production of cellulose film. On the other hand, the presence of patulin in apple juice is a poison that prevents the growth of *Acetobacter*, and the reduction of patulin is done by folic acid and pantothenic acid, while sodium hydroxide, which is a strong base, is considered. As a result, it intensifies the negative effect of patulin.

3-Mateo et al. (2021), in a review study, discussed the products and applications of nanocellulose from agricultural waste. They stated that the separation of nanocellulose from various agricultural residues has become an important research field due to its multipurpose applications. This work collects different production processes, including conditioning steps, pretreatment, bleaching processes and finally purification to produce nanocellulose in its main morphological types: cellulose nanofibers (CNF) and cellulose nanocrystals (CNC). This review emphasizes the importance of agricultural waste in the production of nanocellulose in order to reduce environmental impacts, use fossil resources, ensure sustainable economic growth and close the circle of resource use. Finally, possible applications of nanocellulose as a new source of raw materials in various industrial fields are discussed.

Production of cellulose film from fruit extract or residues of industrial food products containing sugar can be economical. But we are facing challenges and problems such as the presence of previous contaminations or the presence of antibacterial substances, which can prevent the growth of desired bacteria and optimal production of cellulose film.

4-Fatemeh Nouri Rozbahani - Fatemeh Ashrafi - Soheila Moradi Bidhandi: Glycerol and peptone have the most effect in the production of microbial cellulose.

Therefore, to optimize and increase the production of cellulose film from fruit extract, peptone and glycerol can be added to the culture medium and brought to the optimum level.

5-Monaila et al. (2020), in a research, investigated the effect of increasing the scale of the production process on the characteristics and properties of bacterial nanocellulose obtained from the culture medium of overripe bananas. In this study, the effect of bioreactor size was evaluated with regard to the production and characteristics of nanocellulose membranes produced by two different bioreactors: one with a cross-sectional area of 1800 cm² (BCB44) and a laboratory-scale bioreactor with a cross-sectional area of 41 cm² (BC -B1). The cultivation conditions were the same and the substrate consisted of ripe bananas, which are cheap because they are unsuitable for human consumption. The X-ray diffraction pattern showed that the two samples had similar crystal structures, but changes were observed at the morphological level in the nanofibers that make up the BNC membranes. These changes caused changes in the mechanical and thermal properties of the samples. This result demonstrates a novel scaling effect of bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) static state fermentation.

6-Toloui et al. (2014) investigated the synthesis and characterization of bacterial cellulose using *Acetobacter* 10245 xylum ATCC. They stated that the diameter of the synthesized fibers was different and ranged from about 30 nm to 360 nm. Also, the pores had different shapes and their size was about 1 micrometer or more. The fiber length was reported in micrometers. The amount of cellulose produced was directly related to the size of the culture medium in contact with air.

REFERENCES

- [1] آریائی منفرد، ز.، دهقانی فیروزآبادی،. ۱۳۹۷؛ تولید و ارزیابی نانوسلولز باکتریایی با استفاده از باکتری استوباکتر زایلینیوم. پژوهش های علوم و فناوری چوب و جنگل. جلد۲۶؛ شماره ۳، ۲۹-۳۴.
- [2] طلوعی،. س.، کوهی مفتخری اصفهانی،. م.، موحد،. ف.؛ علوی،. اکبرزاده،. ع.؛ ۱۳۹۴؛ تولید و تعیین مشخصات مجله تازه های بیوتکنولوژی *Acetobacter xylinum ATCC 10245* سلولز باکتریایی با استفاده از باکتری سلولی-مولکولی. جلد۵، شماره ۱۸؛ ۴۲-۳۵.
- [3] موسوی لنگری،. س م.؛ نیکزاد،. قریشی،. س ع.؛ محمدی،. م؛ ۲۰۱۸؛ مروری بر انواع نانوسلولز و کاربردهای آن در پزشکی. مجله دانشگاه علوم پزشکی خراسان شمالی. جلد ۱۰؛ شماره ۱، ۵۸-۷۲.
- [4] *Fatemeh Nouri Rouzbahani1 , Fatemeh Ashrafi2 , Soheila Moradi Bidhendi3 . Optimizing the HS medium for the production of microbial cellulose nanofibers using Acetobacter xylinum.*
- [5] *Ahmadzadeh S.1 and Bakhtiari N.1,2. Ursolic Acid: 5 cyclic triterpenoid in apple peel with a wide range of therapeutic effects*
- [6] *Abol-Fotouh, D., Hassan, M. A., Shokry, H., Roig, A., Azab, M. S., & Kashyout, A. E. H. B. (2020). Bacterial nanocellulose from agro-industrial wastes: Low-cost and enhanced production by Komagataeibacter saccharivorans MD1. Scientific reports, 10(1), 1-14.*
- [7] *Akhlaghi, M. A.; Bagherpour, R.; & Kalhori, H; (2020). Application of bacterial nanocellulose fibers as reinforcement in cement composites. Construction and Building Materials; 241, 118061.*
- [8] *Anwar, B., Bundjali, B., & Arcana, I. M. (2015). Isolation of cellulose nanocrystals from bacterial cellulose produced from pineapple peel waste juice as culture medium. Procedia Chemistry, 16, 279-284. doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.proche.2015.12.051*
- [9] *Carreira, P., Mendes, J. A. S., Trovatti, E., Serafim, L. S., Freire, C. S. R., Silvestre, A. J. D., & Neto, C. P. (2011). Utilization of residues from agro-forest industries in the production of high value bacterial cellulose. Bioresource Technology, 102(15), 7354-7360. doi: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2011.04.081*
- [10] *Cheng, Z., Yang, R., and Liu, X. 2016. Production of bacterial cellulose by Acetobacter xylinum through utilizing acetic acid hydrolysate of bagasse as low-cost carbon source. Bioresources. 12: 1. 1190-1200.*
- [11] *Ghasemlou, M., Khodaiyan, F., Oromiehie, A., & Yarmand, M. S. (2011). Development and characterisation of a new biodegradable edible film made from kefir, an exopolysaccharide obtained from kefir grains. Food Chemistry, 127(4), 1496-1502. doi: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2011.02.003*
- [12] *Hadilam, M. M., Afra, E., Ghasemian, A, and Yousefi, H., 2014. Preparation and properties of ground cellulose nanofibers. J. Wood Forest Sci. Technol, 20: 2. 139-149. (In Persian).*
- [13] *Hafsa, J., Smach, M. a., Ben Khedher, M. R., Charfeddine, B., Limem, K., Majdoub, H., & Rouatbi, S. (2016). Physical, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties of chitosan films containing Eucalyptus globulus essential oil. LWT - Food Science and Technology, 68(Supplement C), 356-364. doi: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2015.12.050*
- [14] *Hestrin, S., & Schramm, M. (1954). Synthesis of cellulose by Acetobacter xylinum. 2. Preparation of freeze-dried cells capable of polymerizing glucose to cellulose. Biochemical Journal, 58(2), 345.*
- [15] *Huang L, Chen XL, Nguyen TX, Tang HR, Zhang LM, Yang G. Nano-cellulose 3D-networks as controlled-release drug carriers. J Mater Chem B. 2013;1(23):2976-84. DOI: 10.1039/c3tb20149j*
- [16] *Jia X, Chen Y, Shi C, Ye Y, Abid M, Jabbar S, et al. Rheological properties of an amorphous cellulose suspension. Food Hydrocoll. 2014;39:27-33.*
- [17] *John MJ, Thomas S. Biofibres and biocomposites. Carbohydr Polym. 2008;71(3):343-64.*
- [18] *Jozala, A. F., de Lencastre-Novae, L. C., Lopes, A. M., de Carvalho Santos-Ebinuma, V., Mazzola, P. G., Pessoa-Jr, A., ... & Chaud, M. V. (2016). Bacterial nanocellulose production and application: a 10-year overview. Applied microbiology and biotechnology, 100(5), 2063-2072.*
- [19] *Keivani Nahr, F.; Mokarram, R. R.; Hejazi, M. A.; Ghanbarzadeh, B.; Sowti Khiyabani, M.; &*

- Zoroufchi Benis, K; (2015). Optimization of the nanocellulose based cryoprotective medium to enhance the viability of freeze dried *Lactobacillus plantarum* using response surface methodology. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*; 64(1), 326–332.
- [20] Kurosumi A, Sasaki C, Yamashita Y, Nakamura Y (2009) Utilization of various fruit juices as carbon source for production of bacterial cellulose by *Acetobacter xylinum* NBRC 13693. *Carbohydr Polym* 76:333–335. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2008.11.009
- [21] Ludwicka, K.; Kolodziejczyk, M.; Gendaszewska-darmach, E.; Chrzanowski, M.; Jedrzejczakkrzepkowska, M.; Rytczak, P.; & Bielecki, S; (2018). Stable composite of bacterial nanocellulose and perforated polypropylene mesh for biomedical applications. *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research Part B: Applied Biomaterials*; 107(4), 978-987.
- [22] Mahseswari, U., Obi reddy, K., Muzenda, E., Guduri, B. R, and Varada Rajulu, A., 2012. Extraction and characterization of cellulose microfibrils from agricultural residue - *Cocos nucifera* L. *Biomass and bioenergy*, 46: 555-563.
- [23] Mateo, S., Peinado, S., Morillas-Gutiérrez, F., La Rubia, M. D., & Moya, A. J. (2021). Nanocellulose from agricultural wastes: products and applications—a review. *Processes*, 9(9), 1594.
- [24] Molina-Ramírez, C., Cañas-Gutiérrez, A., Castro, C., Zuluaga, R., & Ganan, P. (2020). Effect of production process scale-up on the characteristics and properties of bacterial nanocellulose obtained from overripe Banana culture medium. *Carbohydrate polymers*, 240, 116341.
- [25] Reshmy, R., Philip, E., Thomas, D., Madhavan, A., Sindhu, R., Binod, P., ... & Pandey, A. (2021). Bacterial nanocellulose: engineering, production, and applications. *Bioengineered*, 12(2), 11463.
- [26] Ruka, D. R., Simon, G. P., & Dean, K. M. (2012). Altering the growth conditions of *Gluconacetobacter xylinus* to maximize the yield of bacterial cellulose. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 89(2), 613-622. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2012.03.059>.
- [27] Salari, M.; Khiabani, M. S.; Mokarram, R. R.; Ghanbarzadeh, B.; & Kafil, H. S; (2018). Development and evaluation of chitosan based active nanocomposite films containing bacterial cellulose nanocrystals and silver nanoparticles. *Food Hydrocolloids*; 84, 414-423
- [28] Stevanic JS, Joly C, Mikkonen KS, Pirkkalainen K, Serimaa R, Rémond C, et al. Bacterial nanocellulose-reinforced arabinoxylan films. *J Appl Polym Sci*. 2011;122(2):1030-9.
- [29] Wang, Y.; Zhang, R.; Qin, W.; Dai, J.; Zhang, Q.; Lee, K.; & Liu, Y; (2020). Materials & Design Physicochemical properties of gelatin films containing tea polyphenol- loaded chitosan nanoparticles generated by electrospray. *Materials & Design*; 185, 108277.